

Is Blood in Urine Associated with Acrophobia?

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ABSTRACT

People having acrophobia show different responses when reaches to some height and can release some chemicals due to which blood in urine can be found. Affiliation of erythrocytes in urine with acrophobia is the particular objective of this study. The existence of erythrocytes in the urine is known as haematuria. It can be non-harmful for the human body or it can affect the urinary system. Fear of height is a term used for acrophobia. Fear from tall building and from steep slopes are the various things that cause fear. Acrophobia is instinct in animals and humans. Total 100 candidates were convoluted in this project. They were students of Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan. They were about 18-22 years old. Urine test of every student was performed to check the level of erythrocytes present in the urine. Then blood in urine was correlated with height phobia. It is inferred from the results that height phobia has affiliation with blood in urine.

Keywords: Urine, Acrophobia, Erythrocytes, Urinary tract.

1. Introduction

The existence of erythrocytes in the urine is known as haematuria. It can be non-harmful for the human body or it can affect the urinary system. Haematuria varies from mild to acute. In mild type, the blood cell present in the urine can only be visible through microscope in acute type, the blood cells can be seen through the naked eye and urine color becomes red or brown. Blood is leaked into urine from any part of the kidneys or urinary tract. E.coli bacteria is the cause of haematuria infect the bladder. 5% of people having microscopic hematuria 40 % of people with visible hematuria suffer from cancer of kidney, bladder, testes, and prostate. Haematuria causes urinary tract infection, kidney stones and may lead to bladder cancer. In other cases of haematuria are kidney and bladder stones, inflammation of the urethra and a genetic disorder. To prevent haematuria the patient should take plenty of water avoid to use harsh chemicals like antiseptics and should try D'Mannose.

Fear of height is a term used for acrophobia. Fear from tall building and from steep slopes are the various things that cause fear. Acrophobia is instinct in animals and humans. Height phobia is more usually found in females rather than it found in men. It inadequately disturbs the lifestyle of women. There are many reasons of height phobia like dizziness, terrified feeling, spinning and headache etc. The daily activities can be interfered. Treatments are available to combat this fear.

The scientific workers has already been correlate different parameters to the specific topic [1-11]. People having acrophobia show different responses when reaches to some height and can release some chemicals due to which blood in urine can be found. Link of erythrocytes in urine with acrophobia is the particular objective of this study.

2. Materials and Methods

Total 100 candidates were convoluted in this project. They were students of Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan. They were about 18-22 years old. Urine test of every student was performed to check the level of erythrocytes present in the urine. Then blood in urine was correlated with height phobia.

Statistical Analysis

MS excel was used to perform the statistical analysis.

3. Result and Discussion

Has blood in urine any affiliation with acrophobia? It is given in table below. 10% males and females having blood in urine and 85%males having no blood in their urine feels fear from height. 57% females do not have blood in their urine suffers from height phobia. 4% females having blood in their urine and in 29% females blood in urine absent, have no height phobia. 5% males have no height phobia.

Gender	Height phobia		No height phobia	
	Blood in urine present	Blood in urine absent	Blood in urine present	Blood in urine absent
Male	10%	85%	0%	5%
Female	10%	57%	4%	29%

4. Conclusion

It is inferred from the results that height phobia has affiliation with blood in urine.

Declarations

Source of Funding

This research did not receive any grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

Availability of data and material

The authors are willing to share the data and material according to relevant needs.

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